

RELATIONSHIP OF THE ISLAMIC-RELIGIOUS-EDUCATION SUBJECTS AND COVID-19 PANDEMIC ATMOSPHERE TO STUDENT'S RELIGIOSITY

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Abstract - *This study aims to determine how much influence the subjects of Islamic-Religious-Education subjects during COVID-19 pandemic atmosphere on student's Religiosity. This research uses quantitative research with associative methods. The data sources obtained are primary data. The data analysis process uses multiple regression analysis, with Islamic-Religious-Education Subjects (X_1) and Covid-19 Pandemic atmosphere (X_2) as independent variables then Religiosity as dependent variable (Y). The study shows that Islamic-religious-education subjects have a positive and significant influence on student's religiosity. The Covid-19 pandemic atmosphere does not have a positive and significant effect on student's religiosity.*

Keywords: relationship, islamic-religious-education subjects, COVID-19 Pandemic, student's religiosity

I. INTRODUCTION

In 2020 the education sector in Indonesia was affected by Covid-19. This incident did not only occur in Indonesia, but spread throughout the world¹. The new coronavirus or novel coronavirus (nCoV) is a new type of coronavirus that causes a disease called COVID-19². In maximizing Islamic education, the participation of stakeholders is needed to support the success of islamic education, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic makes people have to limit social activities to anticipate the infection of Covid-19. The implementation of social distancing does not only apply in social life, in hospitals and at work but also in the field of education. Indonesia's education sector has felt the impact of the COVID-19 outbreak at various levels of education which resulted in obstacles in the learning process. Luthra & Mackenzi (2020) mention that there are four ways COVID-19 is changing the way we educate future generations. First, that educational processes around the world are increasingly interconnected. Second, redefining the role of educators. Third, teach the importance of life skills in the future. And fourth, opening up the wider role of technology in supporting education³.

¹ Siahhaan M. Dampak Pandemi Covid-19 Terhadap Dunia Pendidikan. 2020 May 1;20(2).

² <https://covid19.go.id/tanya-jawab?search=What%20is%20virus%20corona%20baru%20dan%20COVID-19?> accessed on October 5, 2020

³ Edi Ismail, Priyanti. *PENGEMBANGAN MODEL PEMBELAJARAN TECHNOPRENEURSHIP BERBASIS E-LEARNING DI ERA PANDEMI COVID-19*. Jurnal Inovasi Pembelajaran Karakter (JIPK) Vol. 5, No. 3, 2020. ISSN 2541-0393 page 1-14

Indonesia is one of the regions in the world affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has resulted in an unprecedented metamorphosis in the education sector. With the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, it is not only the Government that solves problems in the field of education but teachers also think about how the learning process continues to succeed in educational goals in order to educate the nation's next generation (Siahaan, Matdio: 2020)⁴.

The government through the minister of education has closed learning activities that have caused concerns from various levels of society but learning activities must continue, so good cooperation is needed between the school and parents. During this pandemic, parents play a very important role in assisting the students in the learning process in order to realize the success of learning activities during the pandemic.

Education has three terms in Arabic that relate to the meaning of education, namely *ta'lim* (تعلم), *ta'dib* (تعذب) and *tarbiyah* (تربوية). The word *ta'lim* is *masdar* (مصدر) from the word *'allama* (علم), which means teaching that provides or transfers understanding, knowledge and skills. The word *ta'dib* (تعذب), is the *masdar* (مصدر) of *addaba* (عذب), which means the educational process is more focused on fostering and perfecting students' morals or character. The word *tarbiyah* (تربوية), is *masdar* (مصدر) from the word *rabba* (رب), which means paying attention, educating and nurturing. Education is guidance or consciously given by educators to students in physical and spiritual development towards maturity and so on towards the Muslim personality. Muhaimin said that Islamic education is an effort to understand the content of the Islamic religion and its values to students so that they can become a way of life⁵. In a further sense, Islamic education can be realized in: (a) All the abilities that a person does to instill and develop Islamic teachings and values. b) All phenomena of encounters between two or more people whose impact is the embedded or growing development of Islamic teachings and values on one or several parties. So, Islamic education is the process of forming one's character according to the teachings of Islam to achieve success in the hereafter⁶.

Zakiah Daradjat argues that the purpose of Islamic education is "to form people who believe and fear Allah for the rest of their lives, and die even when they are Muslim"⁷. Mulyasa explained that the purpose of Islamic Religious Education in schools is to grow and increase faith through giving and cultivating knowledge, appreciation, practice, and experiences of students about Islam so that they become Muslims who continue to grow in terms of faith, piety, nation and state, and to be able to continue on to a higher level of education⁸.

According to Hasbi Ash-Shidiqi, the main discussion in Islamic religious education consists of: 1) *Tarbiyah jismiyyah*, namely various forms of education that prioritize the health of the human body so that humans can face various life problems. 2) *Tarbiyah aqliyah*, are various forms of education that aim to educate the mind and sharpen the brain

⁴ Siahaan, Matdio. Dampak Pandemi Covid-19 Terhadap Dunia Pendidikan. Jurnal Kajian Ilmiah (JKI). ISSN: 1410-9794 page 73-80

⁵ Rozi MA. Profesionalisme Guru: Antara Beban dan Tanggung jawab. EDUKASI: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam. 2015 Nov 1;3(2):949-59.

⁶ Suropto S. REVITALIZATION OF ISLAMIC EDUCATION EPISTEMOLOGY. EDUKASI: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam. 2018 Nov 1;6(2):125-36.

⁷ Akmal Hawi. Kompetensi Guru Pendidikan Agama Islam. Jakarta: Rajawali Pers, 2014, p. 19

⁸ Ibid, page 21

3) *Tarbiyah adabiyah*, various forms of education that aim to improve good behavior. *Tarbiyah adabiyah* or character education in Islamic teachings is one of the main teachings that must be taught so that people have and carry out noble character as exemplified by the Prophet Muhammad⁹.

Glock and Stark in Ancok, Djamaludin et al¹⁰ argue that there are five components that make up human religiosity, namely: 1) Faith, is the degree to which humans can accept all forms of dogma in their religion. 2) Religious ritual, is a level that describes how a person performs obligations in religion. 3) Experience, is an event or feeling that has been experienced by someone in the past. 4) Religious knowledge, explaining how far a person knows about religious orders. 5) Carry out religious orders, which describe whether a person's behavior is the result of religious motivation or not.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research was carried out using an associative approach that explained the relationship between three variables, namely the content of Islamic religious education, the Covid-19 pandemic period on students' religious attitudes. The research was conducted at *Madrasah Aliyah* Negeri 1 Tulungagung during the months of May to August 2020. The population of the research subjects were 694 students of first and second grade of *Madrasa Aliyah* with details as shown in Table 1.

Based on the population in Table 1 above, it can be determined the number of research samples using the Slovin formula $n = \frac{N}{1+(Ne^2)}$, where n is the research sample, N represents the study population, and e is the margin of error respectively. If $N = 694$, $e = 0.05$ or 5%, the research sample obtained is $253.74 \sim 254$ students.

Table 1. Number of research population

Grade Level	Male	Female	Total
First grade of <i>Madrasa Aliyah</i>	66 Students	259 Students	325 Students
Second grade of <i>Madrasa Aliyah</i>	76 Students	293 Students	369 Students
Total			694 Students

This research was designed to operate three variables, namely the content of Islamic religious education subjects at the *Madrasah Aliyah* level (X_1); Learning in the Covid-19 pandemic situation (X_2); and student religiosity (Y). Sequentially, X_1 and X_2 are independent variables and Y is the dependent variable. This research studies how the relationship between each variable partially and simultaneously. partial relationship study, namely how the influence of X_1 on Y ; and how the influence of X_2 on Y . The simultaneous study of the relationship is how the influence of X_1 and X_2 on Y .

In order to answer the research problem, an accurate research instrument is needed by operationalizing the variables. Each research variable is described into sub-variables then

⁹ Majdid, Abdul, Andayani, Dian. Pendidikan Agama Islam Berbasis Kompetensi : Konsep dan Implementasi Kurikulum 2004, (Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya,2006), 138

¹⁰ Ibid, page 139

the indicators and descriptions are determined while the measurement scale is determined. Based on the operationalization of the variables in **Table 2** below, a research questionnaire instrument can be arranged.

Table 2. Operationalization of research variables

Variable	Sub-Variable	Indicator	Description	Measuring Scale
Islamic-Religious-Education subjects (X_1)	intellectual	Learning discipline	Learn first before learning content is taught	Ordinal
			Doing assignments given by the teacher	
			Do the job seriously	
	intellectual	Verbal Activity	Collect assignments on time	Ordinal
			Dare to express opinions in learning activities	
			Ask the teacher when you don't know	
	intellectual	Listening Activity	Ask a friend who understands better	Ordinal
			Listen to what the teacher says	
			Always tell the truth	
	moral	Self evaluation	Forgive if someone does something wrong	Ordinal
Take responsibility for what you do				
Trying to get something				
moral	Dutiful to parents	Using the right hand when receiving something from others	Ordinal	
		Don't take things that don't belong to me		
		Listening to parents' advice		
moral	Dutiful to parents	Obey the orders of both parents	Ordinal	
		Leave when your parents tell you to		
		Helping parents with homework		
moral	Social	Caring when parents are sick	Ordinal	
		Giving selflessly		
		Maintain good relations with neighbors		
moral	Social	Sensitive and caring for others	Ordinal	
		Throw garbage in its place		
		Community service is a useful activity		
COVID-19	Motivation	The relationship between schools	The teacher asks students how they are before starting online learning pembelajaran	Ordinal

Variable	Sub-Variable	Indicator	Description	Measuring Scale
Pandemic atmosphere (X_1)	and teachers to students to support the learning process		The teacher gives time to students to collect assignments	
			The teacher intensifies communication with parents so that parents support the learning process	
			Teachers routinely provide motivation so that students are always enthusiastic when participating in online learning	
			The teacher gives the learning content first before giving the assignment	
	Parental involvement in assisting the learning process		The teacher always asks students about the learning media used for the online learning process	
			Teachers accept student consultations at any time during the covid-19 pandemic	
			Teachers are very active in providing assistance to students	
			Parents really support their children in online learning with internet's data facilities	
Minat belajar	Student interest in learning process during the COVID-19 pandemic		Parents really understand their children by not telling/interfering with them when the online learning process takes place	Ordinal
			Parents agree with their children taking online learning	
			Students can understand the learning content well during online learning	
			Online learning improves students' skills in technology	
Support	Facilities for supporting the learning process		Students find online learning fun	Ordinal
			students can learn anytime and anywhere	
			students discover new knowledge that has not been obtained	
			Students can interact well with friends and teachers without feeling shy, making students enthusiastic in participating in the learning process	
			Students can use learning tools well	Ordinal
			The environmental conditions at home support good concentration in studying	
			Students easily get learning resources during the learning process	
			Students agree if the school helps provide internet data to support the success of the learning process	
			Internet network connection can be used properly	
			Parents provide their own cellphone facilities for the online learning process	
			The school provides learning modules as learning resources other than the internet	

Variable	Sub-Variable	Indicator	Description	Measuring Scale
Student's religiosity (Y)	Shalat	Shalat Fardhlu and Shalat Sunnah	Fardhu prayer in congregation	Ordinal
			Praying at the beginning of time	
			Praying without being asked by your parents	
Perform the five daily prayers				
Performing Duha prayer				
Performing the tahajjud prayer				
Pay attention to the <i>shaf</i> density				
Pray even though you are busy				
Reading Al- Qur'an	Read and Practice	Always perform <i>wudlu</i> before reading the Qur'an	Ordinal	
		Reading the Qur'an with Tajweed		
		Reading without being reminded		
		Reading the Qur'an after praying		
		Read the Quran every day		
		Likes to learn the contents of the Qur'an		
		Reading the Qur'an with tartil		
Reading the Qur'an in a holy place				
Fasting	Perform obligatory fasting and Sunnah fasting	If I feel uneasy, anxious and so on, I will read the Qur'an	Ordinal	
		Carry out Ramadan fasting during the month of Ramadan		
		Carry out sunnah fasting on Mondays and Thursdays		
		When the time for breaking the fast arrives, hasten to break the fast on time		
			I like fasting because it trains patience	

Result and Discussion

Data from the research sample of 254 students who met the valid criteria were 247 students and 7 students were not valid. The reliability of the instrument obtained by Cronbach's alpha of 0.81 which means that the instrument has high reliability¹¹.

In order to determine the distribution pattern of the research data, a normality test was carried out. The results of the normality test show that the data is normally distributed following a straight line pattern as shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Normality test result

Based on the regression analysis model $Y = a + kb_1 + kb_2$, the following regression model equation obtained:

$$Y = -0,077 + 1,004X_1 - 0,011X_2 \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

As for the positive (+) and negative (-) signs based on the regression equation, it is reinforced by Agus Eko Sujianto (Sujianto, Agus Eko: 2009) where the positive (+) sign indicates the direction of the relationship is in the same direction, while the negative (-) indicates the direction of the relationship, which is inversely proportional to the dependent variable (X) and the dependent variable (Y). The interpretation of these equations can be explained based on the sign of each coefficient. The regression model above can be described as follows:

- The constant value ($a = -0,077$) in Equation 1 of the multiple linear regression above has a negative value at the constant $-0,077$, which states that student religiosity is inversely influenced by the content of Islamic-religious-education learning during COVID-19 pandemic atmosphere.

¹¹ Agus Eko Sujianto. Aplikasi Statistik dengan SPSS '16. (Jakarta: Prestasi Pustaka, 2009).page 97

- b. The regression coefficient b_1 ($b_1 = 1,004$), indicates that each addition (because it is positive) one level of Islamic religious education subjects (X_1) will increase religiosity (Y) by -0.077. And vice versa if the level of Islamic-religious-education subjects (X_1) decreases by 1.004 then the level of religiosity (Y) is also predicted to decrease by 1.004 with the assumption that X_2 remains constant.
- c. The regression coefficient b_2 ($b_2 = -0,011$), indicates that for every decrease (because it is negative) once, the rate of covid-19 pandemic atmosphere (X_2) will increase Religiosity (Y) by -0.011. And vice versa if the level of COVID-19 pandemic atmosphere (X_2) increases by -0.011, so the level of religiosity (Y) is also predicted to decrease with the assumption that X_1 remains constant.

The results showed that the variable of Islamic Religious Education Subjects (X_1) had a significant and significant effect on student religiosity at MAN 1 Tulungagung. This is evidenced by the results of the t test, it is known that the value of t count $>$ t table ($8.821 > 2.014$) and the significance is less than 0.005 ($0.000 < 0.005$) then H_0 is rejected, H_a is accepted which means that Islamic religious education subjects as a variable (X_1) gave a positive and significant influence on religiosity as a Y variable.

The results showed that the Covid-19 pandemic atmosphere (X_2) did not have a positive and significant effect on religiosity (Y). This is evidenced by the results of the t test that the t value $<$ t table ($-0.112 > 2.014$) and the significance is greater than 0.005 ($0.911 < 0.005$) then H_0 is accepted H_a is rejected. So the null hypothesis is accepted, the conclusion is that the Covid-19 pandemic (X_2) does not have a positive and significant effect on religiosity (Y).

From the regression results, if the value is significant ($0.0002 < 0.05$) and F count ($71.683 > F$ table (4.05)), then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. So it can be concluded that the independent variables jointly affect the dependent variable or the content of Islamic Religious Education subjects during the Covid-19 pandemic jointly affect the religiosity of students at MAN 1 Tulungagung.

III. CONCLUSION

The results of the t -test show that H_0 is rejected, H_a is accepted, which means that Islamic religious education subjects as a variable (X_1) have a positive and significant influence on religiosity as a Y variable.

The results of the t -test showed that H_0 was accepted, H_a was rejected. So the null hypothesis is accepted, the conclusion is that the Covid-19 pandemic atmosphere (X_2) does not have a positive and significant effect on religiosity (Y).

The results of multiple regression shows that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. So it can be concluded that the independent variables jointly affect the dependent variable or Islamic Religious Education Subjects during the Covid-19 pandemic atmosphere jointly affect the Religiosity of Students at MAN 1 Tulungagung.

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